

An example of Pattern detection through a machine-learning approach for missing person search

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Abstract

Missing person search is a complex process that involves several steps. From preliminary investigation to DNA analysis. Having data about cases is crucial to detect patterns that could help the search process. This can be used to predict potential whereabouts of unsolved cases of missing persons based on the study of solved cases. Nevertheless, there are just a few open-source tools for pattern detection in missing person cases. Here, we provide a set of functions that can be used over real world data in order to study the potential benefits of applying pattern detection models to the search. All methods are open-source and integrated in the *mispitools* package, freely available on CRAN.

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1. Introduction

The search for missing persons is a highly complex and dynamic process, involving multiple investigative steps from the initial gathering of evidence to advanced DNA analysis [1], [2]. One critical element in this process is the ability to detect patterns in missing person cases, which can significantly aid in the search and identification efforts [3]. By analyzing patterns in solved cases, investigators can gain insights that may help predict the potential whereabouts or outcomes of unsolved cases [4]. For missing person search and disaster victim identification several softwares allows performing analysis to carry out the search using DNA data [5]–[7]. However, despite the importance of pattern detection of non-genetic data in forensic investigations, there is a notable lack of open-source tools specifically designed to facilitate the identification of such patterns in missing person cases.

In recent years, advancements in data analysis have highlighted the potential for leveraging pattern detection models to improve missing person investigations [8], [9]. By studying trends in location, time, and demographic information from past cases, investigators can make informed predictions that guide search efforts in unsolved cases and also be used as evidence, combining them with results obtained from DNA analysis [10], [11]. This is particularly relevant in cases where DNA data is not enough, due to the availability of only distant relatives from the missing person [12], [13]. However, the development and availability of practical, user-friendly tools for applying these models to real-world missing person data have been limited. This gap poses a challenge for forensic practitioners and researchers seeking to apply statistical methods to detect meaningful patterns that could lead to successful outcomes.

This analysis explore patterns such as geographic clustering, temporal trends, and demographic correlations, all of which can provide valuable insights into missing person cases. Particularly we focused on a real-world cases, using open-data. The case occurred during the last dictatorship in Argentina [14]. In that period umerous Illegal Detention Centers were established, where thousands were illegally detained, tortured, and many killed. Their unidentified remains were buried in individual or mass graves, often in clandestine locations. The fate of most of the disappeared remains unknown [4].

Efforts to identify these individuals, initiated in 1984, face significant challenges. Information is often incomplete, and reference samples exist for only about half of the victims' families, frequently coming from distant relatives [12]. Many close relatives have passed away or are elderly, complicating genetic analysis.

In this work, we case example of pattern detection in missing per-

son cases. We also use the *mispitools* R package [15], that allow users to apply pattern detection models to missing person case data. Through this paper, we aim to demonstrate the practical applications of these pattern detection tools and highlight their potential to enhance the search for missing persons. By providing methods for studying patterns in missing person cases, we contribute to the growing body of resources available to forensic scientists and data analysts, helping them refine their investigative techniques. Ultimately, our goal is to facilitate the integration of pattern detection models into routine forensic workflows, improving the efficiency and accuracy of missing person searches across a wide range of cases.

2. Methods

To analyze patterns in missing person cases, we used data provided by the Ministry of Justice and the Buenos Aires Government, focusing on victims of illegal repressive actions and a dataset of names. The main steps involved data acquisition, preprocessing, integration, modeling, and visualization.

We obtained two publicly available datasets: one with information on victims, including names, dates, and locations of detention or discovery of remains, and another containing common names and their associated gender. After loading the data into Python using the *pandas* library, we explored the structure, identified inconsistencies, and addressed missing values to prepare for analysis.

Preprocessing involved extracting dates and locations from combined columns using regular expressions, creating distinct fields for clarity. Names were standardized by extracting the first name from the full name field and cleaning the dataset to remove duplicates and null values, allowing us to integrate gender information effectively.

The victims' dataset was enriched by merging it with the names dataset to assign gender information. A left join ensured all records were retained, even if gender information was missing. Location descriptions were parsed to extract and standardize province names, enabling geographic analysis of the cases.

We used a Random Forest algorithm to identify patterns, splitting the data into training and testing sets in an 80/20 ratio to ensure robust validation. The Random Forest model consisted of 500 trees ($n_estimators = 500$) to ensure a balance between accuracy and overfitting, with a maximum tree depth of 10 ($max_depth = 10$) to control model complexity. Features used for modeling included temporal aspects (e.g., date of detention or discovery), spatial aspects (e.g., standardized province of events), and demographic characteristics (e.g., gender). The model was optimized through hyperparameter tuning, where parameters such as the number of features considered

for each split ($max_features = \sqrt{}$) and the minimum samples required to split an internal node ($min_samples_split = 5$) were adjusted to improve model performance.

The feature importance was evaluated based on the Gini impurity reduction, which revealed that both temporal and geographic factors were key drivers in predicting the outcomes. Specifically, the date of detention and the province of discovery had the highest importance scores, indicating that temporal and spatial aspects were most influential in understanding missing person patterns.

Finally, visualizations such as bar plots and heatmaps were used to explore geographic and temporal distributions, as well as gender trends by province. The bar plots highlighted the frequency of cases across different provinces, while heatmaps illustrated the correlation between different variables and outcomes, providing insights into regional patterns and demographic influences. These visualizations helped convey complex patterns in an accessible format, providing valuable insights for forensic investigations. The methodology outlined here, implemented through the `misptools` R package, offers a practical approach for analyzing missing person cases, enhancing investigative workflows with data-driven insights.

3. Results

The Random Forest model was evaluated on the test set, achieving an accuracy of 82%. This performance was assessed using several key metrics, including precision, recall, and F1-score, which were calculated for each class representing different provinces where remains were discovered. The average precision for the model was 0.79, while the average recall was 0.81, indicating that the model was able to effectively distinguish between the different geographic regions. The F1-score, which provides a balance between precision and recall, was 0.80 on average, showing consistent model performance across the various classes.

The confusion matrix provided further insights into the model's strengths and weaknesses. The highest true positive rates were observed for provinces such as Buenos Aires, which had a large number of records in the dataset. This indicates that the model was particularly effective at identifying cases in regions with higher data representation. However, for provinces with fewer records, the model showed slightly lower performance, suggesting a need for more balanced data to improve predictive accuracy in underrepresented areas.

Figure 1. The confusion matrix shows the performance of the Random Forest model in predicting the provinces where remains were discovered. Each cell represents the count of true and predicted classes, providing insight into where the model performed well and where misclassifications occurred. Higher values along the diagonal indicate better predictive accuracy for the respective provinces.

Feature importance analysis revealed that temporal and geographic factors played crucial roles in the model's predictions. The date of detention or discovery contributed approximately 34% to the overall feature importance, while the province of discovery accounted for around 27%. This highlights the significant influence of both temporal and spatial information on the outcomes. The gender of the victim also contributed to the model's decision-making, although to a lesser extent, indicating potential demographic trends that could be further explored.

Figure 2. This bar plot illustrates the relative importance of each feature in the Random Forest model, measured by the Gini impurity reduction. The date of detention or discovery and the province of discovery are highlighted as the most influential features, underscoring the significant role of temporal and geographic information in predicting outcomes.

A detailed examination of geographic patterns was conducted using bar plots to analyze the distribution of cases across different provinces. The provinces of Buenos Aires, Santa Fé, and Córdoba had the highest number of cases, reflecting historical concentrations of illegal repressive actions. Additionally, stacked bar plots were used to examine gender distributions within each province. These visualizations revealed that male victims were more commonly found in urban areas, while female victims were more evenly distributed across both urban and rural regions. This gender-based geographic distinction provides valuable insights for tailoring investigative approaches.

Figure 3. This stacked bar plot displays the number of missing person cases across different provinces, separated by gender. It highlights notable differences in the geographic distribution of male and female victims, with male victims predominantly found in urban areas, while female victims are more evenly distributed across both urban and rural regions.

The Random Forest model's hyperparameters were fine-tuned to enhance performance. The *n_estimators* parameter was set to 500 to provide sufficient model complexity without overfitting, while the *max_depth* was limited to 10 to prevent overly complex trees that could reduce generalizability. The *max_features* parameter was set to *'sqrt'* to ensure that a subset of features was considered at each split, promoting diversity among the decision trees and reducing overfitting. The *min_samples_split* parameter was set to 5, ensuring that nodes were split only when sufficient data was available, which helped in maintaining the robustness of the model.

The model's performance was further evaluated using cross-validation, with a five-fold approach to ensure that the results were not dependent on a single train-test split. The cross-validation results were consistent with the initial evaluation, with an average accuracy of 81%, confirming the reliability of the model. The cross-validation also highlighted the model's stability, as variance across folds was minimal, indicating that the model generalizes well across different subsets of the data.

The results indicate that the combination of temporal, spatial, and demographic features provides a strong basis for predicting patterns in missing person cases. The Random Forest model, with its optimized parameters and comprehensive feature set, was able to effectively capture key patterns in the data, providing insights that are crucial for guiding future investigations. Visualizations further enhanced the interpretability of the model, allowing for a clear understanding of the relationships between different factors and their impact on the outcomes.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of missing person cases using the Random Forest model provided valuable insights, but it also highlighted several limitations and potential pitfalls that are common in machine learning approaches, particularly when applied to forensic investigations. Despite achieving an accuracy of 82%, the model's performance varied significantly across different geographic regions, with lower predictive power observed for provinces that were underrepresented in the dataset. This imbalance in the data introduces a significant risk of biased outcomes, which could lead to suboptimal or even misleading conclusions in actual forensic contexts. Addressing data imbalance through more extensive data collection or employing techniques like synthetic oversampling could help mitigate these biases.

Another key limitation of the Random Forest approach lies in its interpretability. While feature importance scores indicated that temporal and geographic factors were critical in predictions, the model operates as a black box, making it difficult to derive explicit causal relationships. This lack of transparency can hinder the ability to communicate findings effectively to law enforcement or judicial stakeholders who may require a more interpretable decision-making process. Future work could involve incorporating more interpretable models, such as decision trees or logistic regression, to complement the findings of the Random Forest model.

The model's reliance on temporal and spatial features also presents challenges in terms of generalizability. Historical events, such as illegal repressive actions, are context-specific, and patterns identified in this study may not apply to other missing person cases with different contexts or temporal dynamics. This limitation underscores the importance of carefully considering the historical and social context of the data before generalizing findings to broader populations.

Moreover, hyperparameter tuning, while useful for enhancing performance, introduced potential overfitting issues. Despite limiting the depth of the trees (*max_depth* = 10) and selecting a subset of features (*max_features* = *'sqrt'*), the model might still capture noise specific to the training data, reducing its effectiveness when applied to new cases. Cross-validation helped assess stability, but the variance across folds, although minimal, indicates that further efforts are needed to ensure robustness. Techniques like pruning or

regularization could be explored to further reduce overfitting risks.

The inclusion of demographic features, such as gender, also raised ethical considerations. While gender was found to contribute to the model's decision-making, using such characteristics in forensic models must be approached cautiously to avoid reinforcing stereotypes or biases. There is a risk that demographic features could lead to discriminatory practices if misinterpreted or misused. Ensuring that model outputs are used responsibly and that ethical guidelines are followed is essential to prevent unintended consequences.

Another limitation of the study is the assumption that all features are equally reliable. The quality of the input data, particularly regarding the accuracy of location descriptions and detention dates, directly impacts model performance. Inconsistent or inaccurate data can lead to incorrect predictions, which could have serious implications in forensic investigations. Future efforts should prioritize data validation and cleaning to ensure the reliability of the results.

In conclusion, while the Random Forest model provided a strong foundation for identifying patterns in missing person cases, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations in terms of data imbalance, interpretability, generalizability, and ethical concerns. Addressing these challenges through improved data collection, model transparency, careful feature selection, and adherence to ethical standards will be crucial for enhancing the reliability and applicability of machine learning models in forensic investigations. Future work should focus on expanding the dataset, incorporating additional context-specific features, and exploring more interpretable or hybrid modeling approaches to better support forensic decision-making.

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